

Mixing Potential, Internalizing Efforts of Values, and Increasing Academic Productivity of Students in Indonesia

Muh. Ihsan¹

Lecturer at at the Syamsul Ma'arif College of Tarbiyah,
Bontang, East Kalimantan,

Khumaini Rosadi²

Lecturer at at the Syamsul Ma'arif College of Tarbiyah,
Bontang, East Kalimantan,

Abstract:- The potential of students is one of the gifts and creations of Allah SWT which is very unique compared to His other creations. Its uniqueness can be seen in the ability of these students to change themselves in a more advanced and developing direction, in line with their growth and development. The ability to change students themselves does not take place immediately, but many things that influence and play the most role are the family environment and the world of education, and their association with the community. The method used in this research is a literature review with the keywords potential of students, value internalization, and academic productivity. This approach can at least show two theoretical approaches, namely the internalization of values and academic productivity approaches. The value internalization approach is related to the process of actualizing, and instilling normative values that determine behavior according to academic goals. Meanwhile, academic productivity is related to works that are made independently in the form of finished goods. the potential found is behavior based on scientific values and independence in academic production.

Keywords:- *Concocting, Potential, Internalisasi nilai-nilai, Productivity.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The potential of students is something that is ready to develop or ready to be developed¹. In this connection, Ahmad Amin calls it first nature².

This potential is one of the fundamental aspects besides the other aspects. Mixing the potential in question is of course adjusted to the level of development, biological and psychological through the appropriate level of education as well. Especially efforts to develop the potential that is still hidden are also matched with abilities through the

internalization of academic values and productivity that should be achieved by students.

The facts that occur in the world of education in schools today tend to direct students' abilities to know a lot about academic knowledge conceptually, but in practice, there is still much more of the conceptual knowledge that cannot be actualized in real life, of course, what is meant here is the internalization of academic values and productivity in the form of behavioral appearances that contain elements of academic values. Especially if educators at certain moments are just trying to catch up on the subject matter in accordance with the lesson plan that is prepared based on the existing curriculum. That means that students are directed only to fulfill learning requirements that aim to meet curriculum targets. Even though it is hoped that the education system will be able to bring up many generations who are experts in certain fields of science in accordance with the scientific aspects they are involved in.

Furthermore, Fuad Nashori said that student potential is a good power or strength that has been actualized but has not been optimal or has not been actualized. This strength can be positive, in the form of strength, and negative in the form of weakness.³ Meanwhile, according to Endra K Pihadhi, potential can be referred to as strength, energy, or latent ability that is owned and has not been used optimally. Self-potential referred to here is a power that is still hidden in the form of physical, character, interests, talents, intelligence, and values contained therein but have not been utilized and exploited.⁴ In line with this opinion, according to Hery Wibowo, there are at least four categories of potential that exist in humans from birth, namely brain, emotional, physical, and spiritual potential, and all of these potentials can be developed without limits⁵. Har Tilaar once said that dialogue is the right way to build potential and generate student motivation⁶. Muh. Ihsan, in the book *Generating Potential, Methods, and Means of Student Academic Quality Efforts* explains how to develop the potential that is still in

¹ dept. P & K. (1996) Big Indonesian Dictionary, Balai Pustaka, Jakarta.

² Ahmad Amin, (1998) *Ethics; Moral Science*, CV. Crescent Star, Jakarta, p. 15.

³ Nasori, Fuad. (2003). *Human Potentials*. Yogyakarta: Student Libraries. p. 6.

⁴ Prihadhi, Endra K. (2004). *My Potential*. Jakarta: Elek Media Komputindo, p. 6.

⁵ Wibowo, Heri. (2007). *Ready Profitable Fortune*. Bandung: OASE OF SPRINGS. p. 1.

⁶ Tilaar, HAR, (2000), *Several Indonesian Education Reform Agenda*, Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture, Jakarta.

the context of material that is ready to be developed or ready to be developed⁷. Meanwhile, this research explains how the process of internalizing values and student academic productivity can be seen in the realities of life.

This is also closely related to Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Article 3 reads that national education functions to develop dignified national character and civilization capabilities in order to educate the nation's life and develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear piety to God Almighty, have a noble character, be healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens⁸.

From the description of the experts and the law mentioned above, when viewed at a glance, the aims of education to be directed at how the potential of these students are developed are actually various existences. However, the essence of the purpose of the law is to develop the potential of students through a good and correct education system. That the world of education that has been arranged in such a way is a vehicle for students to have the opportunity to develop their potential so that they can achieve a better and advanced standard of living in the future.

The purpose of the national education system law is noble. The nobility of these goals will be clearly seen if the internalization of academic values and academic productivity is in the form of behavior of knowledge values that have been independently displayed by students in the realities of life. In a sense, not just developing but practicing in social life. It is even clearer if it is seen through the creation of innovative works that are highly competitive in the present and in the future. Furthermore, the approach that researchers use is to look at how references in educational studies interpret potential through actualizing the values and productivity of academic students in Indonesia.

There are two approaches taken, the first is the approach to internalizing values and the second is increasing academic productivity which is analyzed by looking at the format and the final achievement of academic goals. The findings of this study are to bring out potential concoctions in the form of internalizing educational values and academic productivity of students as well as innovations or new findings, both in the form of theoretical concepts and creativity in the form of highly competitive innovative works produced independently by the best sons and daughters of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This discourse on potential in the world of education as an effort to increase student academic productivity uses a descriptive-qualitative library research approach with the main sources being several references related to student potential in educational development and academic productivity. Furthermore, Reyvan Maulid, said that the data collection technique used in the literature review was reading and recording data according to the theme under study⁹.

Lexy J Moleong said that in the literature review, directing and guiding researchers to form research substantive categories in this regard mixes potential as an effort to internalize values and increase the productivity of academic students. These reference sources can be in the form of books, journals, government regulatory documents, or other relevant references. In line with that, Eka Novianto said that the design of this literature study was expected to be able to explore data in depth and develop an understanding of the internalization of values and increase students' academic productivity in terms of educational aspects¹⁰.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mixing potential for the purpose of internalizing students' values and academic productivity, as well as the reference sources obtained are included in three main potentials that must be integrated and balanced. Thus the potential mix includes heart potential, brain potential, and physical potential:

- Physical potential, eyes and ears for example as sensory registration tools; vision and hearing for the brain and heart which are useful for forming knowledge through sensory experience and intuition. Including hands, and feet if trained properly can become a professional athlete or artist. Physicists who are trained and skilled in various movements can be called physical questions (FQ) which complement IQ, EQ, and SQ.
- The potential of the brain, namely as a tool used for thinking, scientific analysis, conducting experiments, proving in order to seek the truth, and as an embodiment is the existence of science, and technological tools which can then realize the dynamics of civilization contained in two things, namely the actualization of values -values and academic productivity generated independently by students which in turn gave birth to the dynamics of civilization based on science¹¹.
- The potential of the heart is as a control center, controlling the balance of consciousness in all life activities. And at

⁷ Muh. Ihsan, (2016) *Awakening the Potential, Ways and Means for improving the quality of students' academic values*, Page moeka, Jakarta, p. 47.

⁸ Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Ministry of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia. Jakarta.

⁹ Reyvan Maulid, 2021, *Data Collection Techniques with Library Studies*, (website: DQLab) <https://www.dqlab.id/teknik-pengumpulan-data->

[sekunder-dengan-kajian-pustaka](https://www.dqlab.id/teknik-pengumpulan-data-), accessed on Monday 7 February 2023, at 16.17. pm.

¹⁰ Reyvan Maulid, 2021, *Data Collection Techniques with Library Studies*, (website: DQLab) <https://www.dqlab.id/teknik-pengumpulan-data-> [sekunder-dengan-kajian-pustaka](https://www.dqlab.id/teknik-pengumpulan-data-), accessed on Monday 7 February 2023, at 16.17. pm.

¹¹ Muh. Ihsan, 2016. p. 25.

the time of processing, the brain, heart, and other physical organs are driven by certain emotional motives (MET) where which is suspected to cause differentiating elements to arise, thereby differentiating the behavior of each individual that appears in the reality of life. This is where the concept of diversity was born. Therefore, it is very unnatural if the behavior of students is displayed in a uniform reality of life. In addition, the liver also functions as a means of manufacturing chemical substances in the human body¹².

Furthermore, it can be said that through MET, the brain can help improve one's scientific intellect (IQ), the heart can shape one's character, nature, character or behavior (EQ and SQ), physical potential can shape one's physical skills (FQ) or one's talent channel through movement and sound activities, all of which form a degree of potential according to the aspect of the science being studied. The scheme is as follows:

Fig 1 Scheme

Dispensing potential is also adjusted to the goals to be achieved which are directed to the pursuit of true knowledge by paying attention to:

- The interests of the state are not the interests of politics and rulers.
- Equitable development of a comprehensive education system.
- Placing potential development whose content is the internalization of values and academic productivity originating from the potential of the nation's children with the principle of equality "no age limit, no racial element, no rich and poor, no social status" which contained in the overall distribution of educational development intended for the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia towards the development of the 2045 Golden Indonesia education¹³.

- The intelligence of students is supported by improving the welfare of education actors, especially educators and education staff by not taking sides with anyone.
- Superior science and technology development goes hand in hand with superior and strong Imtaq development. Imtaq functions as a bastion of humanity in order to help shape and protect and protect an increasingly complex global civilization¹⁴.

Besides that, lifelong learning is also carried out with the aim of educating the nation's children in all aspects of life and to fulfill all of our expectations so that they become superior human beings with Indonesian characteristics after their education is completed. Indicators of achievement are the appearance of academic values and productivity in every student's behavior in social life and the existence of innovative works made independently by the best sons and daughters of the State of Indonesia, which we all love.

The aim of dispensing potential is the internalization of strong student values in the context of self-maturity in advertising, thinking, and student academic productivity which is carried out through the implementation of education. In fact, this leads to empirical facts that are concluded in three main things, namely beliefs, oneself, and the surrounding natural environment where all three contain meanings that must be understood properly and correctly.

Students in learning these three components must be supported by a relevant education system using relevant curriculum and methodology tools which are then carried out by all components of the nation, the primary educator at school or madrasah or wherever they are.

Related to these three components, seen from the aspect of education and the internalization of legal values, for example, namely religious law, natural law, and positive law. And this of course has a very close relationship and can be understood as explained below:

To fulfill their needs, humans must use their potential through various activities. In order for these activities to proceed properly, humans certainly need supporting facilities, say transportation facilities. Transportation runs smoothly of course through good roads. A good road does not just happen. But many things are connected so that a good path is built. Based on the law of the conservation of mass discovered by Antoine-Laurent Lavoisier states that mass cannot be created and destroyed but can be changed into other forms¹⁵. Related to these provisions, concrete or asphalt roads are made based on suitable base materials and that is the principle of natural law. In order for the roads to wake up quickly, the recommendation of religious law, as M. Quraysh Shihab, once said, please help us with kindness. Here it means the need for mutual assistance, the contribution of energy,

¹² Kimball, W. John, 2000, *Biology*, Erlangga, Jakarta, p.235.

¹³ Tola, Burhanuddin, (2003) *Assessment Standards in Class*, Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. Jakarta.

¹⁴ Tola, Burhanuddin, (2003)

¹⁵ Wikipedia, (2022) *Law of Conservation of Mass*, Free Encyclopedia https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hukum_kekekalan_massa. Accessed on Sunday, January 29, 2023 at 02.22 pm.

thought or material¹⁶. Because of that the park was completed.

Transportation is in process and of course needs security so that unwanted things don't happen, such as at crossroads where traffic lights are located¹⁷. And what regulates it is no longer natural law or religious law but positive law of human products. Likewise, the linkages of the three laws are implemented in the reality of human daily life. Such is the internalization of values and academic productivity that students are expected to highlight in this reality. Then in that connection, there is no intention to equate the three laws. That religious law is still religious law, as well as others. However, it must be understood that even though the three are different in terms of form, they have a very close relationship in terms of purpose.

Presumably, this is one example of a relationship in which there are no conflicting elements. If there is a conflict, it is because maybe it is our brain that makes the relationship between the three laws contradictory because of ignorance or indifference.

The conclusion is that roads are built because there are natural ingredients that can be transformed into other forms. Then humans according to religious advice that please help in goodness, it is necessary to work together, and donate energy, thoughts, or material. In order for the roads to be safe to pass, the role of positive law regulates them such as traffic lights or street signs. Thus, one simple example of the results of internalizing academic values and productivity is expected to be actualized by students

IV. MIXING THE POTENTIAL OF STUDENTS

It is known that human beings from birth have potential which contains the qualities of values that are ready to grow and develop. The potential for growth and development is in line with cycles or shifts in space and time. The development of potential in the early stages is a series of changes that are realized carefully and systematically and ultimately produce the seeds of maturity, maturity, and independence¹⁸. JW. Kimball argued that the development cycle is used to explain data changes even though the actual pattern of development varies between individuals and of course experiences overlap in the process of development.

The phase of potential growth and development in relation to the absorption of subject matter carried out by students can be combined into two parts, namely the internalization of academic values and increasing academic productivity as material for analysis.

V. INTERNALIZATION OF ACADEMIC VALUES

The internalization of academic values has four stages, namely absorption, root formation, knowledge ownership and production:

A. Knowledge Absorption Stage

During this stage, students undergo a series of stimulus-response or absorb educational service materials which are internalized to them as a knowledge transfer process carried out by educators using various instructional devices. Here it is not intended to negate the function of the built-in features from a physical perspective. Therefore, what is meant is an embryo of knowledge that is in accordance with efforts to increase productivity and internalize the behavioral values of students. In addition, the embryo of knowledge that is absorbed by students is still within the limits of "carry out a tree that has just been planted". This means that during this stage, the internalized embryo of knowledge has not taken root and is still easily or prone to being forgotten. Therefore, at this stage of absorption, educators must be aware of it, and then repeat or reduce the material as accurately and clearly as possible until they arrive at the assumption that knowledge in the form of embryos absorbed by these students still gives rise to roots or seeds. seeds of behavior change in students according to the knowledge developed or internalized by them.

B. Stage of Formation of Knowledge Roots

During this stage, the embryo of knowledge that is absorbed as the initial stage mentioned above continues to form and strengthen roots, and organize concepts and meanings to something different from before. As a result, certain patterns are formed according to aspects, and potential components that are developed. the formation of knowledge embryos that are ingested or absorbed by students during this formation phase is arranged into special groups, but are still stored in different potential structures, namely maybe in the brain as well as maybe in the heart.

C. Knowledge Ownership Stage

The stage of ownership of knowledge occurs not long after, after the knowledge has had a positive effect on the level of growth and development of the potential displayed in students' daily lives¹⁹. This means that the embryo of knowledge as mentioned above begins to take the form of the structure and special functions it has when it is active in the framework of maturation, maturation of behavior patterns, and so on is formed. This process is then called the stage of ownership of knowledge. The patterns that are formed can be seen from certain behaviors, for example, attitudes, have started to get used to it until it becomes a habit, intellectuality, has become sharp in thinking, and so on²⁰. When this phase

¹⁶ M. Quraysh Syihab, (2002) Interpretation of Al-Misbah Volume 3: message, impression and harmony of the Qur'an, Lantern Hati, Jakarta, p. 10.

¹⁷ Minister of Transportation, Regulation of the Minister of Transportation Number 49 of 2014 concerning Traffic Light Signaling Equipment, Ministry of Transportation RI. Jakarta.

¹⁸ JW. Kimball, 1983, p. 387

¹⁹ Usman, Uzer, Moh., 2001, Becoming a Professional Teacher, PT. Rosdakarya Youth, Bandung, p. 21.

²⁰ Nur, Muhammad, 1998. Cognitive Learning Theory, Teachers' Training College, Surabaya, p. 19.

of knowledge ownership has become entrenched, it then forms the final pattern, namely self-realization that is visible through the internalization of academic values or academic productivity in the form of works that are made creatively, productively, and innovatively with full independence²¹.

D. Stages of the Production Process as the Realization of Knowledge

Production as a series of inventions can occur even as a whole quality of values originating from the potential that has been formed. During this stage, the quality of each value has an important role in life activities²².

However, whatever the actual form and mechanism, the production process as a series of inventions or invention efforts itself is very dependent on the material of the academic learning process that is internalized by students from the educational arena. Therefore, there must be a clear direction and goals to be achieved. Such as industrialization, productivity in the form of innovative work, the formation of civil society, and so on. So, the potential development strategy towards scientific and technological discoveries is based on basic principles, namely: studies and research efforts are carried out intensively to obtain authentic facts, concept studies and designs are made based on meeting needs that are appropriate and relevant to the availability of resources and existing materials, and the last is the processing and production process is carried out based on the results that have been made before. Furthermore, the process of disseminating and marketing educational products in order to meet the basic needs of all human life.

VI. INCREASING STUDENT ACADEMIC PRODUCTIVITY

Academic productivity is an analysis related to educational service materials that have been implemented so far in an education system, it was found that in terms of numbers which seem more towards the fact that knowledge is like a burden rather than something that students should know which at the same time states that this is how that science. This fact can be seen at certain stages and types of education. The type and level of madrasah education at the first advanced level, for example. In each subject chapter, there are approximately 4 sub-chapters. The number of subjects is 15 with 8 chapters per subject that students must know on average per year. So if it is calculated, it is obtained 15 X 8 X 4 per grade level VII, VIII, and IX = 480 types of material from all subjects that students must know for one academic year.

While the actual time spent at school is 7 to 8 hours with a weight of 40-45 minutes per subject per day of the effective time per year or 42 hours per week. It becomes a burden because there is too much that must be known by academic students while the time available is very little and it lasts for one year. Then the rationalization of the potential ability to

develop is calculated based on the circle of space and time multiplied by the number of potential values divided by the number of hours during the day and night to obtain a value of $(360 \times 4)/24=1440/24=60$ K.P/a unit of space and time of day and night education throughout life instead of $1440/8$ hours = 180 K.P/unit of formal school time for one academic year. (K.P.) = potential ability to develop). Meanwhile, P_o is obtained from:

$$P_o = \frac{SPOT \times Tp^\circ \cdot Jp^\circ}{Jp^1/K}$$

$$P_o = \frac{2 \times 4.40}{40/2}$$

$$P_o = \frac{320}{40/2}$$

$$P_o = \frac{8}{2} = 4$$

That is, students are forced to their abilities with a ratio of three times the rationalization of their abilities. So that the material presented is not internalized properly and is even more quickly forgotten. Perhaps this is one of the factors causing the low level of learning achievement achieved by students that have applied so far.

The description above shows that the potential of students regarding material that can be internalized has more or less a strong influence on academic productivity in the process of educational services, as described below:

$$K.P = \frac{N.P_o}{P_o}$$

$$K.P = \frac{60}{4}$$

$$K.P = 15$$

For more details on this relationship, first it is known about: (1) The number of lesson hours and the number of teaching sub-materials delivered to students in one face-to-face hour. The number of lesson hours is one hour with a weight of 45 minutes and the amount of material presented is two to four, so it can be seen as follows:

"Total academic productivity (PAT) for the amount of one teaching material unit (JMA) and the number of one subject unit (SMP) in one day equals (N.Po) The potential value multiplied (Lw) the length of time used, divided by the total one teaching material unit (JMA). To find out the PAT, the above agreement will be derived as follows, "with a note that if the final result of students' total academic productivity (PAT) is obtained below a third of 15 K.P., then the student's PAT is estimated to experience weaknesses and or teaching

²¹ Nasution, Noehi, 1997, Educational Psychology, al-amanah, Jakarta. p. 27.

²² Lauer, H., Robert, 1993, Perspectives on Social Change, PT. Rineka Cipta, Jakarta, p. 93.

materials that are prone to internalization forgotten." The value of this third in this paper is adjusted to the Word of the Prophet, which means that it reads more or less: "No son of Adam fills a container that is worse than the stomach. It is enough for the son of Adam to eat a few mouthfuls to straighten his back. But if he must (exceed it), superior to a third of his stomach (filled) for food, a third for drink, and another third for breathing"²³. That's a full stomach, then what about the brain? therefore the formula was lowered:

$$K.A = \frac{N.Po \times Lw}{JMA}$$

$$K.A = \frac{15 \times 1}{2}$$

$$K.A = 7.55 KP.$$

This value is based on the length of time used for 1 hour and the amount of subject matter internalized as many as 2 face-to-face subject matter turns out to be a value of 7.55 KP. This means that the productivity of academic students is assumed to be strong. Further description:

$$K.A = \frac{N.Po \times Lw}{JMA}$$

$$K.A = \frac{15 \times 1}{3}$$

$$K.A = 5.03 KP.$$

This value is based on the length of time used for 1 hour and the amount of subject matter internalized as many as 3 face-to-face subject matter turns out to be a value of 5.03 KP. That is, students' academic participants are assumed to be at the threshold of being forgotten.

$$K.A = \frac{N.Po \times Lw}{JMA}$$

$$K.A = \frac{15 \times 1}{4}$$

$$K.A = 3.02 KP.$$

This value is based on the length of time used for 1 hour and the amount of subject matter internalized as many as 4 face-to-face subject matter turns out to be a value of 3.02 KP. This means that the productivity of academic students is considered very weak. Because of that teaching with 4 subjects per day with 4 sub-materials per subject is really worth abandoning. Don't empathize, three are still worth considering.

Table 1 Information²⁴

Simbol	=	Information	Value category
K.P	=	Potential ability to develop	15 (static)
N.Po	=	Potential Value	60 (static)
Po	=	Potential	4 (static)
KA	=	Initial ability	Dynamic
Lw	=	Length of time used	Dynamic
JMA	=	amount of teaching materials in one hour	Dynamic
JMP	=	the amount of teaching material in one day	Dynamic
SPOT	=	Sulbi and sternum	2 (static)
K	=	The essence of life and motion	2 (static)
Jp°	=	The number of each stage of development in the uterus	40 (static)
Jp ¹	=	Human development time limit from birth	40 (static)
Tp°	=	Changes in appearance in the uterus	4 (static)

Based on the explanation above, it can be interpreted that students' academic productivity can be achieved well if it is supported by a good education system, a curriculum that is appropriate to the level of biological and psychological development of students. This means carrying out the curriculum while still paying attention to the ability of students to produce and not seem to feel pressured just for reasons of pursuing the target curriculum. Furthermore, to determine the progress and increase in productivity, it is necessary to carry out intensive and continuous control.

VII. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTERNALIZATION OF VALUES WITH INCREASING STUDENT ACADEMIC PRODUCTIVITY

There is no doubt that the internalization of values is a series of ways to instill academic values in students. Internalization of these values is in the form of habituation attitudes so that students who participate in the habituation chance to become accustomed to behaving based on the knowledge they have learned. Likewise honing intellectual abilities so that they are sharp, and intelligent in expressing their thoughts in the reality of life also based on the knowledge that has been learned. As with habituation, sharpening intellectual abilities, training skills so too. Thus, the internalization of values that are firmly ingrained in students can later become a strong energy and motivation for increasing student academic productivity. The productivity of these academic students is in the form of a real role model for others in behaving, the appearance of this behavior appears in an inseparable whole regarding these internalized

²³ Mustika Rahayu, (2019) Eating and drinking patterns according to the hadith of the Prophet, (a study of

Tahlili), Journal of Islamic Discourse, Vol. 7 number 2. p. 298.

²⁴ Muh. Ihsan (2016), p. 50

components²⁵. In addition, academic productivity can also be in the form of scientific works produced by students according to the aspects of the knowledge they are practicing. So it can be said that at the beginning is the internalization of values and in the middle is a strong energy that becomes the driving force and in the end, is the emergence of productivity. Then this driving energy is the link between the internalization of values and the increase in the productivity of these academic students. So in the world of education, the motivation to build is far more important than banning subject matter.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The results found in this study are that education is a vehicle for channeling the potential of students, both physical, brain, and heart potential. However, it should be remembered that learning should not be impressed as a burden as a result of efforts to fulfill curriculum targets, but rather as a vehicle that aims to gain knowledge. Because the potential in question includes physical potential, brain potential, and heart potential which are formulated in such a way, the educational goals to be achieved can also be realized. In order for this potential to reap good results, compounding must go through the appropriate educational arena and of course, the result is that behavior is based on scientific values that have been internalized and there is also academic productivity in real life. Or translated into social life that directs itself independently according to the aspects of knowledge that are involved and with the character and characteristics of each student.

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²⁵ Cece Wijaya, 2021. p. 45.